

More than newspapers

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Trove was never one thing. When version 1.0 of Trove was released by the National Library of Australia in November 2009, it brought together a range of existing discovery services. Some of these had their own long histories. Libraries Australia, for example, contributed millions of catalogue and holdings records from libraries around the country to Trove. But Libraries Australia itself was only the latest incarnation of the Australian Bibliographic Network, established in the early 1980s. Picture Australia was one of a series of specialised portals absorbed into Trove. Launched in September 2000, Picture Australia was an early example of how metadata could be aggregated from multiple collections to provide a single search interface. Similarly, Australian Research Online built on collaboration between universities, research agencies, and the National Library to enable users to search across research repositories and collections of digital theses. And then there was Pandora, established in 1996 as one of the earliest efforts to archive the web itself. Pandora was uncomfortably bolted on to Trove, as the National Library sought to provide users with a single point of discovery for Australia's cultural collections.

But Trove, as we know and love it, tends to be identified with a single, more recent initiative. The Australian Newspapers Beta site was released to the public in July 2008, preceding Trove itself by more than a year. The newspapers service differed to most of the other components that Trove brought together. Instead of harvesting metadata records and pointing to resources elsewhere, the newspapers service delivered digital copies of original publications. The digitisation process segmented newspapers into individual articles, and extracted the text content by Optical Character Recognition. Combined, these two processes made it easy for users to search the full text content of thousands of newspapers across hundreds of years, finding articles on almost any topic. It was truly revolutionary.

It's no surprise that the digitised newspapers have come to dominate our perceptions of Trove. But by focusing on the newspapers, we risk losing sight of Trove's ambitions, tensions, problems, and possibilities. Trove is still a work-in-progress, and as researchers we should think about what it might be, as well as what it is.

The scale of Trove is measured in millions. The 'Image, Maps & Artefacts' category holds details of 5.6 million resources; 'Books & Libraries' over 23 million. There are 230 million articles from newspapers and government gazettes, and billions of archived web pages. Yes, *billions*. Finding relevant information at this level of scale and diversity can be a challenge, and sometimes the organisation of resources seems confusing or contradictory. Users might wonder, for example, why the *Australian Women's Weekly* can be found amongst the digitised newspapers, while *The Bulletin* lives in the 'Magazines & Newsletters' section. It has little to do with their content or format, instead it reflects changes in Trove's funding and back-end processes. Trove's history affects how we use it.

The 2020 Trove update rearranged the existing content 'zones' into 'categories'. The new 'Magazines & Newsletters' category usefully exposes articles from a wide range of

digitised periodicals, but the boundaries are still unclear. Records for the digitised periodicals themselves seem mostly to be in 'Books & Libraries', along with digitised books and ephemera, born-digital publications submitted through the National eDeposit service, and records from Libraries Australia. Digitised government publications, such as parliamentary papers and annual reports, are split between the two categories. Like the location of the *Women's Weekly*, the reasons for these sorts of inconsistencies are complex – a mix of metadata quality, information flows, technological limits, and the desire to maximise findability. The point is that there is no 'natural' arrangement – decisions have to be made for practical reasons, but they're not fixed or final. Instead of worrying too much about the overarching logic, perhaps we should focus instead on developing and sharing strategies for discovery across Trove. Search itself is a research method, and in a resource the size of Trove we should expect to spend time learning and documenting its quirks.

I've been adding many Trove tools, workarounds, and hacks to the GLAM Workbench.¹ For example, I've harvested lists of digitised books, periodicals, and government publications and shared them as standalone databases to provide direct access to resources, including the full OCRd text. Or perhaps you'd like all the *Women's Weekly* covers from 1933 to 1982? Or a collection of 3,471 full-page editorial cartoons from *The Bulletin*? Discovery comes in many forms. By sharing these sorts of collection 'slices', we leverage our own specialised knowledge to help others find relevant resources. And you can do this without any technical knowledge – simply by adding urls to all the digital resources you cite in your next published paper, you can turn it into a subject-specific finding aid!

Searching at Trove-scale creates opportunities for serendipitous discovery, but it can also obscure patterns and connections. Trove harvests information from hundreds of organisations, large and small – libraries, museums, archives, universities, government agencies and more. Each record is indexed and thrown into the mix, but while individual records become findable, their parent collections lose shape and coherence. For example, within Trove's 'Music, Audio & Video' category are details of more than 400,000 programs and segments broadcast of ABC Radio National from the 1990s to the present. It's a rich record of political and cultural life over the last few decades, but how do you know it's there? Similarly, 'Books & Libraries' contains details of more than 300,000 interviews, speeches, and press releases from federal politicians harvested from the Parliamentary Library. As a standalone dataset, this collection could support research into changes in political language, or media reporting. The GLAM Workbench includes tools to harvest and explore these collection, as well as some pre-harvested datasets to get you started.

What's not in Trove? What's hidden? What's incomplete? The GLAM Workbench slices the complete digitised newspaper corpus in different ways to explore its contents and context. By charting the number of articles over time we can, for example, see how funding decisions and copyright policies have affected the selection of newspapers for digitisation. Another example looks for patterns in the correction of OCRd newspaper text – what gets corrected and why? You can also look for newspapers with non-English language content, or articles published after 1954's 'copyright cliff of death'. As

¹ GLAM Workbench, <https://glam-workbench.net/>

researchers we should ask questions about how collections like Trove's newspapers are constructed and what this means for our use of evidence.

Much of this analysis is possible because Trove exposes data through an Application Programming Interface (API). While the web interface is designed for humans, the API helps machines build queries and process results. The API lets us move beyond the search box to see Trove differently. For example, the GLAM Workbench includes the latest version of QueryPic, a tool I created to visualise searches in Trove's digitised newspapers. Instead of a list of search results, you see the number of matching articles per year – a chance to track trends and explore change over time. To dig deeper, you can use the Trove Newspaper Harvester to download newspaper articles in bulk. Other examples analyse OCRd texts, map places of publication, or visualise differences in archived web pages. APIs are cool, but using them does require some technical knowledge. The GLAM Workbench tries to build skills and confidence by providing a mix of tools and documentation. QueryPic is a simple web app that anyone can use, but you can also dive into the code if you want to find out how it works.

However, the Trove API itself has inconsistencies and limitations. Not all data is available, and sometimes the GLAM Workbench has to resort to hacks and workarounds to fill these gaps. For example, the API doesn't provide information about which issues are available for digitised periodicals, even though this information is displayed in the web interface. Last year's update put the web interface and API even further out of sync, as the API knows nothing about the new top-level categories. Once again, we need to be prepared to ask critical questions about the limits and assumptions of online resources.

Access is a collective responsibility. GLAM institutions, like the National Library, need to be open about the policies and practices that shape their resources. But researchers need to be honest about their methods, and ready to learn. Trove is not one thing. It is an attempt to bring together cultural heritage collections and deliver new means of discovery and use. Trove is revolutionary. Trove is flawed. It is inspiring and annoying – seemingly limitless, but full of holes. Trove is a start, but not the end.